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Some Remarks About the Foundations of Quantum Mechanics

Spiros Koutandos

Phd in superconductivity, Maniakiou 17, Agia Paraskevi, Attica, Greece

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ABSTRACT: We give in short a possible explanation of the existence of spin in quantum mechanics and present a summary of our 35 year research on the foundations of quantum mechanics

KEYWORDS: Quantum Mechanics, Foundations Spin in Five Dimensions, Hidden Variables.

INTRODUCTION

We have come to some conclusions after 35 years of research on the hidden variables of quantum mechanics regarding some theoretical framework on which quantization may be explained.

We believe that a ring is rotating in five dimensions creating closed surfaces of simultaneity which in turn create volume vibration waves. Those are the longitudinal photons. Vibration of volume necessarily creates uncertainty in measurement.

MAIN PART

The symmetry breaking in the collapse of the wavefunction destroys superposition. This results in the loss of spacetime symmetries which may result in disorientation but the formation of a monopole antimonopole pair from the momentarily transformation of the mass as an inherent property of the spin makes up for it.

The two monopoles formed North and South are sources of curvature for spacetime. They also mark the beginning and end of classical time. They are warps of spacetime. The spin which is responsible for this is regarded as rotation of the point particle but in its quantum frame of reference it is the universe that is rotating.

Spin exists in five dimensions as a rotating ring. This is why we can not measure simultaneously all its projections in the axes. As the ring rotates it creates a polarization wave. Mass is associated with spin. This is why the photon has zero spin.

CONCLUSION

The results exposed are only a short summary of our findings. As we celebrate 100 years of quantum mechanics in 2025 a book is going to be published from Greece discussing in depth the foundations of quantum mechanics. We hope we have contributed to this field of research and hope there will be peace in the world.

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